

Assessing Challenges of Enforcing Water Pollution Control Regulations on “Small Business Enterprises and, Artisanal and Small-Scale Mining Activities” in the Developing Countries: Zimbabwe Perspective

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Abstract:

Economic paradigm shift from large scale activities to small-scale activities evolving in Zimbabwe, has resulted in emergence of unique wastewater generating sources, characterized by large numbers and ability to be nomadic, moving from one location to another, leading to the phenomena of shifting water pollution sources. This assessment found how challenging implementation of water pollution control legislation for regulatory authorities is, due to absence of ‘economies of scale referencing’ in the legislation which primarily had been drafted for large scale economic activities. Small business entities find it difficult to apply and pay for pollution fees as the legislation currently consider wastewater generators similarly, without factoring in production scales. Micro, small and medium

enterprises (MSME) evade water control regulations by installing illegal discharge channels which are easily concealed to regulators and some resort to night operations to avoid scrutiny. Lack of appropriate and affordable technology for small scale wastewater treatment, is another hinderance to successful implementation of water pollution control regulations. Highly, spaced pollution sites of MSME affect the ability of regulatory authorities to visit all sites and carryout effective monitoring for adherence to water pollution control legislation. Zimbabwe, to achieve halving water pollution as envisaged by Sustainable Development Goal (SDG6) need to cover all sources of water pollution by empowering the small enterprises sector by availing financial incentives for development of low-cost wastewater treatment technologies for use by this sector.

Keywords: *Abattoirs, Small-scale mining, Backyard Industries, Water pollution, Wastewater Discharge Standards.*

Introduction

Water is fundamental requirement for life and very little progress has been done to find alternative solvents with similar

qualities(Pohorille & Pratt, 2012). UNICEF reports that about 4 billion people globally experience severe water scarcity at least one month per year, drivers of water scarcity include

malfunctioning water systems, discharge of partial and untreated wastewater into water resources further worsened by impacts of climate change (unicef, 2024). UN attaches importance to water resources, hence its assignment of SDG6 for water and sanitation provision. Increasing global population has ensued sustained increase in global wastewater generation from anthropogenic activities, currently estimated at 360 billion m³ annual and only 52% is collected and treated leaving 48% discharged into environment untreated (Jones et al., 2021). Economic activities play a significant role towards wastewater generation sources affecting both quantity and quality.

Impacts of anthropogenic water pollution sources have been controlled and mitigated by enactment of water regulation and policies in different countries like in United States of America and Europe they promulgated Clean Water Laws and Water Framework Directives respectively (Gonzalez Zapata et al., 2024). Similarly, Zimbabwe's principal water pollution control legislation is Environmental Management Act, Chapter 20:27 ("Environmental Management Act," 2002) which is premised on polluter pays principle (PPP) as part of United Nations Rio Declaration on Environment and Development. The policy envisages that those who produce pollution should bear the costs of managing and preventing damage to human health and the environment (Luppi et al., 2012). Implementation of water pollution regulations has been successful in curtailing excessive release of pollutants into water resources from traditional water pollution sources in developed countries and to some extent in developing and transition countries as well. However, progressive change in economic activities in the developing countries has seen an emergence of small-scale business enterprises coupled by small scale mineral extraction and processing which have affected water pollution control regulations implementation.

Zimbabwe experienced rapid growth of small-scale business enterprises and small scale mining activities mainly from the years 2008 to date, this paradigm shift has presented unique

environmental pollution centers which are diverse and many thus possess a threat to water resources (Mubonderi, 2023). Small businesses and informal industries have sprout around urban centers especially along water ways and streams, such industries do not install any wastewater treatment plants and are not connected to local authority sewerage system, hence they discharge direct to surface waters causing massive pollution (Nyamangara et al., 2008). Ambient water in the vicinity of artisanal mining activities continue to record deteriorating water quality due to excessive release of process water contaminated by mining chemicals, as a result increased concentrations of ammonium nutrients and nitrates are recorded (Dube et al., 2024) which leads to eutrophication in surface water bodies. Uncontrolled mercury discharge from artisanal small scale gold miners (ASGM) into water resources results in bioaccumulation of mercury in fish species which is detrimental to human health and ecological safety (Makaure et al., 2023).

Whilst, small business entities and small-scale mining activities have been hailed in the alleviation of poverty in the developing countries, their water pollution contributions and adherence to water pollution regulations have been overlooked. Available, studies mainly focus on water pollution regulations adherence by large scale pollution entities such as urban municipalities, thermal power stations and large-scale mining conglomerates. This study assesses challenges associated with enforcement of water pollution control regulations within the micro & small business enterprises, small scale and artisanal mining areas. Systematic review of information on challenges gathered through accessing government reports, water pollution control legislation implementing institutional reports, interviewing environment officers, international organizations reports, media articles and published articles, was done.

Water Pollution Control Legislation and Institutional Arrangement in Zimbabwe

The country has three national legislation which directly deals with water pollution control and regulations, see **Figure 1**, that shows legislations and institutional arrangement, with the constitution specifying that “every person has a right to an environment that is not harmful to their health and prevention of pollution”. Overall, pollution control standards are mainly found in the Environmental Management Act, CAP 20:27 which its enforcement is done by, Environmental Management Agency. The other

two institutions are, Zimbabwe National Water Authority (ZINWA) which is mandated with management of water resources and the Department of Environmental Health Services, mainly mandated with water & sanitation provisions and monitoring of drinking water sources.

At local government level, local authorities both urban and rural implement all the provisions of the three legislations however through by-laws which are applicable to specific administrative boundary controlled by individual local authority.

Figure 1. Legislation and Institutional Arrangement for Water Pollution Control

Source: Public Health Act, 2018; Water Act, 1998; Zimbabwe National Water Authority Act, 1998; Environmental Management Act, 2002

Key provisions of the Environmental Management Act, Cap 20:27, to begin with, is requirement of **wastewater treatment**, in addition the **treated effluent has to comply** with water pollution control **standards**, furthermore the treated effluent is to be discharged under a **permit**. Environmental Management Agency, is to employ enough environmental inspectors and officers who carry out compliance monitoring within effluent generating entities, to ensure adherence to wastewater discharge standards.

Wastewater Treatment Plant Requirement

The legislation makes it mandatory that any effluent generating entity should install wastewater treatment plant before discharging into environment. Whilst the legislation does not prescribe the type of wastewater treatment technology to be installed by polluters, wastewater compositions influences the required treatment plant to be used. Industrial effluents are highly variable with great pollution load and are better handled in a more advanced treatment technology. Establishment of wastewater treatment plant requires financial injection and

technical skills for the operation of installed plant, this exact extra costs to the pollution generating entity. Studies have revealed the variation in wastewater treatment costs largely depending on various factors such as treatment level, technology, capacity, emission standards and location of plant (Lyu et al., 2020; Niu et al., 2016; Ozgun et al., 2021).

Wastewater Discharge Standards

The national regulations currently specify 48 parameters and their permitted discharge standards limit to be reached by treated effluent,

before its discharged directly into environments. Zimbabwe uses concentration based effluent discharge standards, see Table 1, with Bulawayo local authority sewerage system discharge limit for trade effluent (Gumbo, et al., 2003) included for comparison. It can be noted, Bulawayo limits are higher than, national standards because, national standards represent standards for direct discharge to environment whilst local by-laws limits, effluent is discharged into local authority sewerage system where effluent is further treated to reach levels of national standards.

Table 1. Selected Parameters for Effluent Discharge Standards

Parameter	Unit	EMA criteria – National limits					Bulawayo By-law limits
		Blue		Green	Yellow	Red	
		Sensitive	Normal				
Ammonia (N)	mg/l	≤0.5	≤0.5	≤1	≤1.5	<2.0	-
BOD	mg/l	≤15	≤30	≤50	≤100	<120	-
COD	mg/l	≤30	≤60	≤90	≤150	≤200	<2 000
Total N	mg/l	≤10	≤10	≤20	≤30	≤50	-
Total P	mg/l	≤0.5	≤0.5	≤1.5	≤3	≤5	-
TSS	mg/l	≤10	≤25	≤50	≤100	≤150	<2000
SS	mg/l	-	-	-	-	-	<600
Cyanide (CN ⁻)	mg/l	0.07	0.07	0.1	0.15	1	<10
Soaps*, oils, grease	mg/l	Nil	2.5	5	7.5	10	<10
Detergents	mg/l	0.2	1.0	2	3	5	-
Iron	mg/l	0.3	1	2	5	8	<25
Lead	mg/l	0.05	0.05	0.1	0.2	0.5	<10
Cadmium	mg/l	0.01	0.01	0.05	0.1	0.3	<10
Chromium	mg/l	1	1	1.2	1.6	2	<10
Zinc	mg/l	0.3	0.5	4	5	15	<15
Temperature	°C	25	25	35	40	45	<45

Source: Environmental Management (Effluent and Solid Waste Disposal) Regulations, 2007; Gumbo, et al., 2003

On the national standards four classes with different colors are designated, representing the level of pollutant concentration to be reached by treated effluent. These colors show environmental risks associated with effluent pollutants, starting from safe (Blue color), low risk (Green color), moderate (Yellow color) and high risks (Red color) with effluent beyond, red class category not acceptable to be discharged into environment.

Discharge Permits

As the legislation is premised on PPP, discharge of effluent requires a permit. The cost of

quarterly discharge permit follows the four-class category of the discharge standards and is calculated as follows, equations 1, 2 and 3 with less stringent class attracting higher discharge fees.

Yellow Class Example Calculation

$$\text{Annual registration + monitoring} = \text{Fixed Amount} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Yellow class quarterly discharge license cost} = \text{Annual monitoring fee} + (0.015 * \text{Volume discharged}) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Total license fees} = \text{Fixed Amount} + \text{Quarterly fee} \quad (3)$$

Source: Environmental Management (Effluent and Solid Waste Disposal) Regulations, 2007

N.B: Annual registration and monitoring are fixed by the government as at when need arise either due to currency value or recommendations by experts or regulator or interested parties. Trade effluent license, fees are determined by the respective local authorities.

As can be seen from above equations no categories for different sizes of wastewater generating entities, all in spite of differences in economies of scale same calculation method is applied.

Influence of Economic Activities on Water Pollution Sources

Wastewater has been defined as water that has been used in the home, in a business, or as part of an industrial process. Zimbabwe, had its economy largely agro-based, where large scale agricultural activities were mostly preferred livelihood activities, also due to presence of rich mineral deposits big scale mining operations were common, most wastewater point source generation were associated with largescale agro-based industries, manufacturing industries and large-scale mineral processing plants. Economic activities largely influence the sources of wastewater, the country has experienced economic meltdown since the turn of the new millennium due to unsuccessful economic policies and impacts of climate change, economic activities started shrinking from large scale operations to micro-business enterprises and on the mining sector emergency of small scale mining operations increased, as the economic situations deteriorated worse, small scale mining operations expanded to include artisanal mining operations.

Figure 2. Geospatial Distribution of MSME in Zimbabwe
Source: FinScope, 2022

The country 2022 survey reported 1 954 202 MSME exist, with annual turnover of US\$14.2 billion, Figure 2, shows their spatial distribution and its evident from the map these are more concentrated in urban centers cutting across the entire country. Sectors surveyed include agriculture or farming, wholesale or retail, tourism, manufacturing, business services, construction, community & household, natural resources & mining and other activities(FinScope, 2022). As a result, the country has mostly small business enterprises and small-scale mining, being important wastewater generating entities. The government

is continuing the promotion of various MSME in various sectors of the economy through various programs hence, their wastewater management practices have to be controlled.

Characteristics of Water Pollution by MSME

This study characterized small business enterprises into four groups clustered according to similarities in their operations and wastewater generations, see Table 2 (Appendix), whilst Figure 3 shows moveable gold processing plant, used by small scale gold miners, which is easily transported from one site to another.

Figure 3. Moveable Gold Processing Plant -Hummer mill

Source: Photo taken by Ndiweni, K.

Experiences and Challenges in Implementation of Water Pollution Control Regulation on MSME

General the present environmental legislation was mainly drafted for bigger polluters, however the reality on the ground is that more and more micro industries, businesses / enterprises are coming up, and becoming a threat to wastewater management. The effect of having many MSME,

means *elevated costs* of regulatory services as many individual points have to be visited for compliance monitoring and testing of effluent discharges from the various point sources. Implementation of water pollution control laws and regulations on MSME has been characterized by several challenges in many parts of Zimbabwe and alike in other developing

countries, which are further separated into broadly following categories:

Illegal installations

MSME due to their reduced operation scale, are able to install illegal discharge channels which are difficult to trace by regulators, sewage systems operators and most of the illegal installations are diverted into stormwater drainage system and public streams. In Bulawayo city, it is common knowledge that some streams receiving such illegal discharges such that, pungent smells associated with public streams have led to naming of such streams with names reflecting associated water pollution “*Mazai* and *Phekiwe*”, which former referring to bad smell produced by rotten eggs and latter, refer to state of being cooked (Ncube, 2023; Ndlovu & Mpala, 2020). Similarly, in Mashonaland central, “*Yellow Jacket*” river getting the name from color of water in the river, which is brownish-yellowish due to pollution from mining activities. Sometimes, MSME start as illegal operations without proper following of guideline installations and therefore their operations are mostly not in conformity to general wastewater management standard practices. Regulators end-up being at loggerheads with operator when insisting on installation of proper wastewater treatment facility.

Nomadic polluters

Some MSME sources of pollution are mainly occupied by temporary owners and embark on seasonal operations. Operators continual change without any notices to regulators and hence regulators find challenge in the monitoring of their activities. The latest manufacturing plants and processing plants, are becoming easy to install and dismantle e.g. hammer mills and ball mills used by small scale and artisanal miners. The miners carry them from one point of operation to another depending on the availability of mineral resources and or sometimes closer to water resources to access process water. Portable processing equipment allows MSME to evade compliance monitoring by shifting operating hours from day time to, night time operations. In some cases, manufacturing plants are installed within home

premises and are concealed, with effluent being released into water ways or transported to be disposed offsite without any prior treatment.

High pollution fees

Economies of scale in relation to discharge permits or regulations applications are critical in water pollution control regulations, the legislation implementing PPP should clearly highlight the categories. Absence of clear categorization of water pollution fees for MSME and large-scale operators in current Zimbabwe water pollution control legislation, exposes the MSME to financial burden due to high pollution fees. This promotes discharges of wastewater illegal by MSME as they avoid registration and payment of discharge fees.

Lack of appropriate and affordable wastewater treatment technology for MSME

Limited availability of appropriate and affordable wastewater treatment technologies for various MSME, general available treatment technologies are both costly and difficult to operate, hence compromising ability to acquire wastewater treatment plants. MSME who are willing to comply opt to install substandard technology resulting in discharge of poor effluent and disapproval of their wastewater installations by regulators.

Technical limitations

Lack of ability to measure pollution by regulatory authorities due to absence of appropriate equipment, is a challenge for pollution monitoring from these operations. MSME do not have environmental systems and are incapable of self-monitoring. As a result, some water pollution remains undetected until it has accumulated since its released in small quantities by the MSME however cumulatively being massive.

Polluter resistance

Regulatory authorities are facing polluter resistance during enforcement, this can either be direct or passive. Environmental Management Agency report unwillingness by MSME to comply with water pollution control regulations. Direct resistance, polluters refuse to be engaged

by regulatory authorities. Passive resistance, polluters promises to adhere to all the requirements of legislation and promises to start the processes, but eventual changes operation mundus, like re-locating the premises or operational area and changing operational times.

Lack of knowledge

Reduced knowledge on requirements of water pollution control regulations by MSME exacerbate the non-compliance to water pollution regulations by MSME.

High operational costs

MSME reports that inclusion of wastewater treatment processes on their operations increase's overhead costs, which affects their viability, hence preferring to engage in illegal discharges of effluent to avoid losses.

Additional challenges associated mainly with artisanal and small-scale gold mining (ASGM)

Insecurity of regulators

Prevalence of violence within ASGM operational areas is very common and such violence deters fair application of water pollution control regulations in some areas, as environmental inspectors avoid venturing in those areas fearing for their security (Mkodzongi, 2020).

Interference on regulators work by high public profile people and politicians

ASGM has largely been associated with poor rural Zimbabweans, however this has shifted significantly with mining sector becoming the most viable and rewarding livelihood activity, its operations have been hijacked by ruling elite (Hwehwe & Thebe, 2021). The elites now control the bulk of registered mining claims, sponsor the ASGM by supplying operating equipment and consumables, these people operate through representatives. However, the challenge with elites owning small scale operations is using their various official public offices positions to evade requirements of the water pollution control legislation.

“Amakorokoza” challenge

This category of miners is very difficult to handle for regulators as mostly work illegal on either registered mining areas or unregistered mining areas, hence they refuse responsibility of operations and the bonafide mine claim owners, also refuse to take responsibility.

Involvement of local community

Involvement of local communities in the small-scale mining activities presents, difficult situation for regulatory authorities to enforce, water pollution control regulations. Community members, have limited capabilities to put proper water pollution control installations and systems.

Slow policy alignments

Delayed policy response by government due to lack of understanding the magnitude of impact caused by MSME on environment. The government for a longtime propagates inconsistent policies which allows MSME wastewater generators to continue disregarding adherence to water pollution regulations. For example, Zimbabwe government continue to buy gold from artisanal miners, though in terms of current mining legislation artisanal mining is not fully supported by legislation.

Conclusions

The assessment concludes that a combination of factors such as lack of knowledge and education about water pollution control regulations among small business enterprises are leading factors resulting in impediments on legislation and regulation implementation. Absence of appropriate consideration by water pollution control legislation of operational scale is a deterrent to adherence to regulations requirements by MSME, hence need some serious considerations. Movable processing plants used by MSME make it easier to avoid water pollution control registration process. Synchronization of policy pronouncements and changes through various regulatory authorities is required to reduce mismatch of legal requirements on businesses. Speeding up processes of legalizing small-scale and artisanal mining, can greatly aid the implementation of

water pollution control legislation. The government and local government through responsible organizations are recommended to carryout awareness and training on water pollution control regulations across sectors of MSME and such programs should be ongoing.

Conflict of Interest

No conflict of interest

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Appendix

Table 2. Characteristics and Incidences of Water Pollution by MSME in Zimbabwe

Small business enterprises		Extent in the country	Description	Effluent characterization	Impacts and Risk assessment	References
1	Abattoirs Poultry Piggery	Moderate	Mostly found in peri-urban area, rural growth points and farming areas Abattoir or slaughter house washings are mainly directed into a nearby pit or released directly into open surfaces or waterways	Effluent contain animal blood and manure waste, its high in pathogens, high organic content. Elevated levels of BOD, COD, microbial content, suspended solids, fats & oils	HIGH Effluent causes eutrophication and depletion of oxygen in water bodies; spreads diseases Ground water pollution is inevitable as unlined waste stabilization ponds are used In a study conducted on Bulawayo abattoirs effluent was found to contain high pathogens	(Gufe et al., 2021)
2	Car washing centers Vehicle workshops Open space mechanics	Moderate	Offer services of car washings, commonly located in the high-density areas and central business areas of urban centers Car washings are directed into pits or storm drains Effluent is generated from cleaning off of vehicles	Effluent contain detergents, oils and suspended solids, however sometimes gets diluted due to high volumes of added raw water Elevated contaminants such as petroleum hydrocarbons, surfactants, asphalt, organic matter, heavy metals	HIGH A study conducted in Chimanimani car washes; high values of BOD, COD, oil & grease were found on the river receiving effluent	(Danha et al., 2014)
3	Small Scale miners and Artisanal miners	Severe	Mainly located in the peri-urban, rural areas and farming areas (or general countryside). Small scale miners mainly operate from designated mining claim. The most common are into gold mining and processing, effluent is generated during either extraction as dewatering and mineral processing. However, unique characteristics of artisanal miners is that the operations mainly are not confined into a designated mining claim, but only the presence of mineral deposits is considered	Effluent has high content of heavy metals and also gets contaminated with other chemicals like mercury, cyanide, acids, blasting chemicals (nitrates) Elevated levels of COD, heavy chemicals	HIGH In a study conducted under Umzingwane Catchment, water quality tests showed high concentration of nutrients such as ammonium and nitrates, in ambient water, which was linked to activities of small-scale mining such as use of ammonium explosives. Water resources, directly polluted by small scale mining have been reported across the country, such as in Penhalonga area and Alexander Lake, Mutasa District where mercury and cyanide concentrations above permitted limits have been detected.	(Dube et al., 2024) (Matiashe, 2023)

4	Back yard industries and home industries	Severe	Located in urban centers, comprise of a mixed sector e.g. manufacturing of detergents to mineral processing such as gold. Some locations contain scrap metals as well for salvaging purposes	Highly varied effluent, however can contain both organic and inorganic pollutants at high concentrations, like traditional effluent from convectional industries	<p>HIGH</p> <p>In a study conducted on surface waters around home industries were found to contain high levels of phosphates, Faecal matter, ammonia, iron and lead in Harare</p> <p>Mukuvisi river, Harare has been receiving industrial effluent from MSME as some have noted penalty for polluting rivers is cheaper than cost of treatment</p> <p>The practice is common to other urban centers, where small industries avoid treatment by direct releasing raw effluent to streams in the vicinity</p>	<p>(Amon Murwira, 2014; Mvungi et al., 2003)</p> <p>(Nyamangara et al., 2008)</p>
Comments						
Absence of sanitation facilities around operational areas of MSME, makes open defecation to be prevalent especially in the small-scale mining areas, where bush is readily available as they are hesitant to build a temporary toilet. Open defecation result in faecal contamination of water resources in the vicinity environments.						(Munyoka, 2020)